

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND STYLES AMONG ACADEMIC LEADERS IN A STATE UNIVERSITY: AN ANALYSIS USING THE THOMAS-KILMANN MODE INSTRUMENT (TKMI)

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes responses and attitudes of academic leaders in the workplace manifesting strategies to conflict, specifically in a state university and uncovered the different management styles adopted by them in conflict situations. A mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research designs, was used to analyze responses of 30 participants designated as deans and chairs of the different colleges in Isabela State University through an in-depth face to-face interview utilizing a semi-structured guide questions and focus group discussion. Data gathered were collated, recorded and formed into themes and analyzed through thematic analysis. To determine the conflict management styles of respondents, the researcher adopted the Thomas and Kilmann Mode Instrument (TKMI) which consists of a 30-pair statements to identify respondents' preferred conflict-handling style based on the five modes of avoiding, competing, accommodating, comprising, and collaborating. Results revealed that strategies to conflict include proactive approach in management, adherence to established policies and standards, participative decision making and laissez-faire style of management. These highlighted the need to provide training programs for leaders to enhance conflict resolution skills, encourage open communication, adopt the principle of rule-based leadership focused on rules and procedures and encourage active participation of the employees in decision-making and allowing a wide a range of freedom to make decisions on their own. It also revealed that the conflict management styles adopted by school managers using the TKMI leaned towards the medium range between

25-75% with avoiding as the highest followed by compromising, accommodating, collaborating and the lowest being the competing style respectively.

Keywords: *Conflict, conflict management, conflict strategies, conflict management styles, organizational conflict*

INTRODUCTION

Numerous findings are provided by existing literature about conflict and conflict management in various settings but only few are geared towards determining how school leaders specifically respond to conflict and conflict situations particularly in an academic setting. How a leader responds to any misunderstanding, dispute or discord among members of an organization is likely to depend on knowledge and experience why these occur and the expectations of the parties as well. Managers respond to conflict situations differently from others. Other may consider the occurrence of conflict as a positive driving force that aids the organization improve its performance, while others may view the same as a negative phenomenon which greatly impact organizational efficiency. Findings in various studies concluded that school managers or leaders respond to conflict in ways they deem best or according to what the situation demands. Their attitudes vary according to circumstances, organizational structure and power dynamics in an organization.

A significant role played by academic leaders include adopting conflict resolution strategies to effectively respond to conflict. Different types and nature of conflict call for different approaches and may significantly impact the outcome either mitigate or prevent or to some extent even aggravate the same. This is an affirmation of the findings by Sudhakar (2023) emphasizing that causes of conflict are greatly attributable to parties in it, their relationship with one another and the social structure of the organization in place. Leaders may find help from those provided by various theories suggesting different reasons for conflict and the appropriate strategies to deal with them which largely depend on varying theoretical orientations applicable.

According to a study conducted by Folger et al. (2001), conflict can be described either as productive and unproductive, depending on how the same is managed. According to Perkins (2003), the elements required for collaboration to exist give rise to constructive conflict, while their absence results in unproductive conflict. Furthermore, a number of writers concurred that interactions leading to constructive conflict are prerequisites for good conflict management. Therefore, Lynn Fitzpatrick, R. (2007) contends that proactive conflict management, or taking action to promote productive conflict and decrease unproductive conflict, occurs when one expects to act beforehand to handle unforeseen obstacles. She further argues that a proactive approach to conflict management can be taking the connotation that one should concentrate on achieving what one wants (collaboration) rather than responding to what is actually occurring in the business. Consequently, it is claimed that establishing alignment among organizational members demonstrates proactive traits that aid in their readiness to cultivate progressive conflict,

which advances organizations. Simultaneously, a bottom-up information flow and a multifaceted "employee opinions" play an increasingly important role in leadership decision-making and, consequently, improve performance, which is increasingly dependent on the active participation of the organization's employees in decision-making (Chang et al., 2021; Jia et al., 2021). This is because modern information technology integration has emerged. In his seminal study "Management by Objective," the management guru Peter Drucker also believed that encouraging employee involvement is a crucial component of effective leadership, according to Wang et al. (2022). In reality, a number of well-known businesses and organizations have gradually incorporated employee participation behaviors in decision-making into the dynamics of the organizational process.

One continuing tendency among school administrators or leaders is to use established policies or procedures as a means of resolving conflicts amongst faculty members. This establishes the rule-based leadership philosophy, which is an approach to organizational leadership that emphasizes following rules and processes in order to accomplish goals. One feature of bureaucratic leadership is rule-based leadership (Abun, 2021).

To assess a person's behavior, the Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (TKMI) is utilized. An individual's behavior in conflict situations can be characterized by two basic dimensions: (1) assertiveness, or the degree to which the person attempts to handle their own difficulties, and (2) cooperativeness, or the degree to which the person attempts to address the concerns of others. These two behavioral factors can be used to classify five different dispute resolution approaches. Recent social science researches have produced a modest body of literature that divides interpersonal conflict-handling techniques into five categories. This classification was first put forth by Blake and Mouton (1964), but Thomas (1976) later revised it. Consisting of accommodating, avoiding, compromising, contending, and collaborating are its five modes.

According to Thomas's (1976) interpretation, the plan is based on the two distinct aspects of cooperation: assertiveness, which is concerned with trying to address one's own issues, and cooperation, which is about trying to meet the needs of others. Furthermore, aggressiveness and uncooperativeness are associated with competing, assertiveness and cooperation with cooperating, assertiveness and uncooperativeness with avoiding, assertiveness and cooperation with accommodating, and a balance between cooperativeness and assertiveness with compromising.

Research Questions

The research endeavors to answer the following questions:

1. What are the conflict management strategies of respondents to conflict situation?
2. What are the conflict management styles of respondents in dealing with conflict according to the Thomas-Kilmann Mode Instrument (TKMI)?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study and participants

The study involves academic leaders of Isabela State University System which has 11 satellite campuses in the Region. Respondents are academic deans and program chairmen of the different colleges in the campuses, purposively chosen as respondents.

Research Design

The study used the mixed method of qualitative and quantitative research. The descriptive qualitative method was employed in exploring and analyzing the responses of a total of 30 participants designated as deans (15) and chairs (15) of the different campuses at Isabela State University. A descriptive qualitative research design facilitates the identification of a population's or a phenomenon's features or spot trends in the traits that a group possesses. When a straightforward description of an event or experience is required, one that concentrates on the specifics of what, where, when, and why is employed, or when a clear description of experiences and perceptions is needed, especially in areas where little is known about the subject under investigation, a qualitative descriptive design is employed (Doyle et al., 2019)

Responses were collected from participants through an in-depth face-to-face and focus group interview utilizing semi-structured self-made guide questions. The researcher explored the participants' responses by collecting information on their conflict management strategies towards attaining its specific objectives. This method allowed researcher to gather data from them, after which responses were recorded and analyzed, emerging themes or patterns were coded to make meaningful interpretations through thematic analysis. The goal of thematic analysis is identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within data. It is referred to as a descriptive approach that, when combined with other data analysis techniques, reduces the data in a flexible manner (Castleberry & Nolen, 2018). Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was employed with selected respondents to validate quantitative data and to gather supplementary input to fully attain the objectives from respondent deans and program chairmen (Guiab & Miguel, 2023).

For the quantitative part of the study, a total of 122 participants, 21 deans and chairmen 101 chairmen participated in the survey and answered the questionnaires distributed to them.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The respondents of the study which include the deans and program chairmen of the different colleges of the campuses in Isabela State University were selected through purposive sampling. A total of 21 deans and 101 program chairmen participated and responded.

Research Instruments

The research instrument consists of two (2) parts: I. Guide questions utilized for the face-to-face or online interview of respondents for the qualitative part and II. Survey Questionnaires utilizing the Thomas-Kilmann five (5) modes of Conflict Management Styles and the Thomas and Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (MODE) for conflict management. For the qualitative part, the researcher used a self-made semi structured guide questions to elicit responses from the participants which included six (6) major questions with sub-questions and follow-up questions the researcher deemed necessary to gather additional responses if objectives were not fully accomplished.

For the quantitative part, the researcher utilized a survey questionnaire adopted from the Thomas and Kilmann Mode Instrument (MODE) which consists of a 30-pair statements which are lifted from the Thomas and Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument which identifies a person's preferred conflict-handling style based on the five different modes—avoiding, competing, accommodating, comprising, and collaborating.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study were obtained from respondents after which the face-to-face and on-line interview (for respondents from Palanan campus and those unable to do face-to face) and focus group interview according to respondents' availability. Questionnaires and other data were distributed per campus and collected upon completion and others were collected after a few days upon completion.

Data Analysis

The data responses obtained from the face-to-face and on-line interview and focus group interview were analyzed through thematic analysis where responses were coded and analyzed and formed into meaningful patterns or themes. General emerging themes were deductively formed into specific themes.

For the quantitative part, the following statistical tools were used:

To analyze the conflict management styles or strategies adopted by school managers/leaders in dealing with conflicts using the Thomas Kilmann Mode Instrument, frequency and percentage were employed.

Percentage was utilized as a statistical tool to analyze and represent the distribution of responses, particularly in identifying the conflict management styles or strategies adopted by school managers and leaders and to quantify the frequency and proportion of respondents selecting specific conflict management styles, allowing for an interpretation of how prevalent each style is within the population studied.

Percentile scores to be used and its interpretation shall be based on the following:

0 to 25	Low
26 to 75	Medium
76 to 100	High

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Conflict Management Strategies

Analyzing the individual responses of respondents resulted to the emergence of the following responses and attitudes of school managers and leaders to conflict situation defining their conflict management styles which have been accordingly coded into the following themes:

1. Proactive Management Approach

The theory of proactive conflict management, a defining characteristic of transformational leadership, may serve as the foundation for proactive conflict management as a perspective on conflict situations. The greatest way to deal with problems that could cause conflict or a crisis is to take a proactive approach. Anatsui and Ojunita (2015) supporting this point of view, stating that the best way to manage a crisis is to ensure that one does not occur by implementing a regular, planned, and sustained strategy, or by taking the necessary precautions to stop a crisis before it arises. This is regarded as being planned, proactive, and preventive.

This attitude is shown in making emphasis on anticipating issues and addressing them early or when a school manager actively seeks to resolve conflicts before they escalate by understanding and addressing root causes as confirmed by a program chair when she shared that *"I usually give time and talk to them to avoid further escalation."* (Respondents 21, personal communication, March 25, 2024) Likewise, this involves understanding underlying issues and addressing them comprehensively (Northouse, 2016) by conducting a thorough investigation to identify the real causes of conflicts and implementing strategic solutions. A seasoned school managers shares that his secret in dealing with any conflict in the workplace is a resolved attitude of calmness and empathy saying that he does not act immediately, or make a decision hastily hearing out first what the parties have to say.

Thus, it is shown that transformational leadership results in improved outcomes for individuals, teams, and organizations. However, the description of a transformational leader is very idealistic and wide-ranging, and includes a number of personality traits, rather than learned skills. Indeed, a transformational leader is often conceptualized as a heroic leader who establishes the direction and vision for the company; this contention implies a less democratic approach and places the onus on the leader to motivate followers to achieve organizational goals.

2. Adherence to Established Policies and Standards

Participants claimed that when confronted with conflict situation, they tend to refer to established guidelines and policies in resolving the same. Two of the program chairs revealed in their statements affirming the above-mentioned saying: *“I see to it that clarificatory manner is brought to proper office”* and *“always seeking for approval of higher authority, especially if it concerns urgent matters, may be done right away, if not, raised in proper forum.”* (Respondents 11 and 19 personal communication, March 25, 2024). In case where other responses and attitudes to conflict situations manifest where no applicable rules or guidelines may be applied to resolving the same, a problem however may occur. When respondents were asked how to resolve an ensuing conflict in the absence of established rules and procedures to settle the same, one department chair readily expressed that *“in cases where there are no appropriate policies to apply, “Sometimes past experiences and those learned from previous trainings or seminars as applicable to the given situation may be used as reference.”* (Respondents 13, personal communication, March 20, 2024.). Other respondents added, *“Otherwise, use common sense, follow what is morally right and acceptable.”* (Respondents 14, personal communication, March 20, 2024.)

These answers are consistent with the Transactional Leadership theory, which holds that leaders should guarantee that followers follow policies and guidelines (Bass & Bass, 1985 quoted by Antonakis & House, 2012). This is designed to strengthen organizational structure and discipline and guarantee that issues are resolved through the appropriate channels. This same mindset is shown when administrators and heads of schools try to match choices to policies and procedures, placing a strong emphasis on following organizational guidelines in order to resolve disputes. By doing this, executives guarantee that choices are made in accordance with the regulations in place, ensuring consistency and justice inside the organization. Because they consistently refer to authorities when conflicts arise according to routine, transactional leaders hold authorities in high regard. This is to guarantee that important matters are addressed.

3. Open Communication and Participative Decision Making

Transparency and communication among team members, according to participants, are claimed to be necessary in dealing with conflict. A manager listens to both sides of a conflict to ensure a balanced and just resolution. This is reflective of the Participative Leadership Model, which according to Miao (2013) is where leaders involve all parties in the decision-making process to ensure fairness and manifest that supervisors elicit higher levels of trust and leads subordinates to reciprocate through exhibiting higher levels of organizational commitment in which the leader involves subordinates in the process of problem-solving and decision-making. These principles are exactly what almost all deans and chairmen respondents believed as they expressed *“I usually try to work on what solution I could give that will satisfy both ends, “I allow parties to offer solution suitable to all”, “I listen to them and agree to arrive at what is beneficial to the organization” and “I try to understand their perspectives and respect their opinion.”* (Respondents 2, 8, 11 & 17, personal communications, March 20, 2024.) All of the aforementioned answers are ideal

representations of the mindsets and strategies of managers who consistently work to find a win-win solution. reflecting the goal of finding solutions that completely satisfy all parties, as stated in the Thomas Kilmann Mode Instrument by Thomas & Kilmann (1974). Under this, administrators at schools collaborate with both sides to comprehend their viewpoints and come up with a solution that works for everyone.

4. Laissez Faire Management Style

Participants admit to adhering to a laissez faire management style. This leadership style is letting parties work out their differences amicably. In general, laissez-faire refers to an economic theory that supports little intervention by the government in the economy, according to Cornell Law School (n.d). It is said that a Laissez faire leadership style gives employees a lot of freedom to make decisions on their own. Leaders do not really participate and would not comment on employees' activities unless asked; this is very much a hands-off approach (Houlihan, 2020). The phrase literally translates to "let them do it," but the figurative meaning is somewhat closer to "leave them to do it."

Managers in the workplace don't always decide what to do when problems arise. They go, allowing the parties to resolve their differences amicably on their own. The study's participants are quick to admit that this is how they have always handled disagreement. A college dean as saying, *"I will wait for them to ask me to resolve the conflicts since they are now of the right age and I believe in their maturity, I am giving them the chance to resolve conflicts on their own."* (Respondent 5, personal communication, March 19, 2024.) Another chair of the department agrees to this saying, *"I wait for them, not immediately talk to them, to speak out and give freedom to share their feelings towards the situation."* (Respondent 8, personal communication, March 19, 2024.) Another respondent has seen the advantages of this attitude to conflict saying that *"Yes. Because it is better for them to talk out their differences and settle it by themselves."* (Respondent 3, personal communication, March 19, 2024.) Likewise, other respondents subscribe to these views because they believe *"parties will have more time to think about the situation and their behavior"* and *"because I know that they are mature enough to come up with solutions for themselves."* (Respondents 6 and 9, personal communication, March 19, 2024.) Similarly, the deans and chairs who were interviewed expressed that they allow them to do what they want to do with the hope that it will bring enlightenment to the conflict.

It is important to highlight that this mindset is associated with trust-based passive laissez-faire leadership. However, according to Thanh and Quang (2022), this approach is only applicable when working with employees that have a high level of responsibility and self-discipline. In contrast, it will be challenging to accomplish leadership goals with employees who lack discipline. According to Norris et al. (2021), this is essentially "the absence of leadership." Scholars have traditionally dismissed "laissez-faire leadership" as the actions of incompetent managers who are uninterested in the results of their organizations or their followers. When workers are subject matter experts in their fields, this kind of leadership is appropriate. A department chair articulates this idea more clearly when she says, "I rely on them to resolve as they are considered professionals." I will only

meditate when things get really bad. (Respondents 23, personal communication, March 19, 2024) This illustrates the drawbacks of this mindset by demonstrating how poorly handled, laissez-faire leadership inside the company can have detrimental effects and generate stress in workers. In contrast to the traits of transformational and transactional leaders, Yang et al. (2015) claim that these leaders are passive and not strategy-oriented.

B. Conflict Management Styles or Strategies Adopted by School Managers using the Thomas- Kilmann Mode Instrument (TKMI)

Figure 1. Conflict Management Styles or Strategies Adopted by School Managers using the Thomas and Kilmann’s Mode Instrument (TKMI)

Accordingly, this table shows that the conflict management styles or strategies adopted by school managers using the TKMI leaned towards the medium range between 25-75% with avoiding as the highest with 60%, followed by compromising with 56%, accommodating with 49%, collaborating with 43% and the lowest being the competing style with 33%. The raw scores are transmuted to smaller number in order to represent smaller value for easier understanding. This is derived by dividing actual score/total responses x highest score to get the equivalent raw score.

A medium range of 60% on avoiding styles suggest that respondents are unassertive and uncooperative. As to Thomas (2008), when an individual adopts this method, they fail to promptly resolve their own issues or the other person, or they fail to confront the conflict directly. Avoiding can include ignoring a problem, delaying it to a more convenient moment, or just pulling away from an impending circumstance. According to Nischal (2014), the avoidance style of conflict management has a low assertiveness and cooperativeness level, making it suitable for situations where the issue is deemed unimportant. This can also be apparent when the people involved in a dispute appear to be acting indifferently or refusing to take action. This attitude is consistent with the respondents' statements that unresolved complaints resulting from school managers'

failure to take appropriate action was one of the sources of conflicts they faced. According to Harlos (2021), unresolved issues can raise intentions to leave the company and lower job satisfaction.

Another mode used by respondent managers is compromising which is still within the medium range comprising 56% in percentile score. According to Thomas (2008), compromise is the process of finding a rapid solution that all parties can agree on. It sits somewhere in the midst of assertiveness and cooperation. This mode recommends doing more than competing but less than accommodating because it is in the center ground between the two. In contrast to avoiding, it addresses a problem more directly but does not delve as far into it as collaborating does. It takes a middle-ground position or makes concessions. The administrators of the schools demonstrated this approach in their handling of conflicts when they admitted that it would have been better to encourage compromise or mediation as a way to get the parties to lay their cards on the table and then motivate them to find a middle ground. This is in line with the conflict management model developed by Thomas and Kilmann in 1974, according to Benke (2023), which names the compromise approach as one of the five conflict-handling strategies. In order to establish a solution that is at least somewhat acceptable to all parties, this model offers a more cooperative and compromising approach.

A considerable 49% represents the accommodating style which according to Thomas (2008) is a conflict management style which is both unassertive and cooperative and it happens to be the opposite of competing. When such style is adopted, one neglects his or her own concerns just to be able to satisfy the concerns of the other parties because the element of self-sacrifice in this mode is prevalent. Accommodating style leads one to display selfless generosity or charity yielding to another's point of view, even when one prefers not to do normally. Some of the notable manifestation is when school managers feel they are outmatched and losing and believes more competition would only damage the cause. A person who adopts this style deems it best to preserve harmony and avoiding disruption. This approach is consistent with the claims made by school administrators that supervisors at work do not always decide what to do when disagreements arise. They go, allowing the parties to resolve their differences amicably on their own. Study participants are willing to admit that this is how they have always handled disputes. In a similar vein, the interviewee deans and chairs stated that they permit their members to pursue their interests in the hopes that it will shed insight on the matter at hand.

Another conflict handling style is collaborating style which is 43% falling within the medium range. Thomas (2008) claims that this management style fosters the strength of agreement and views others outside the team as possible allies in addition to viewing teammates as allies. Its key components include listening to others and expanding on their thoughts. The key objectives of this method are consensus, open-mindedness, and learning how to blend one's own views with those of others to arrive at win-win solutions. The respondents' disposition toward using inclusive and participatory decision-making in conflict situations is an example of this style. This is a great fit for the approach to addressing conflicts that managers take, which involves attempting to find a win-win

solution and balancing the situation. seeking solutions that completely satisfy each and every party. Additionally, According to Nischal (2014), a collaborative approach scores highly on assertiveness and cooperativeness. It is frequently portrayed as a win-win situation in which all parties involved are happy with the resolution's conclusion and both sides actively engage toward attaining the goals.

Lastly, the competing style with 33% is still within the medium range of the percentile rank. While this may be considered to be the lowest among all five, it is still notably within the middle range. The win-lose strategy is another name for the competing method. High assertiveness and minimal cooperation are characteristics of this management style, which aims to achieve one's own desired results at the expense of other parties. This strategy might be useful in emergency situations or other situations where prompt, definite action is required. Furthermore, Khanaki and Hassanzadeh (2010) believe that this style is used when a person only considers achieving their own goals at the expense of other parties involved and employs all necessary strategies to succeed. Furthermore, the goal of competing strategy is to increase or acquire authority and power. According to London et al. (2019), conflict and power are linked. Conflicts are largely caused by the hierarchical frameworks and power disparities found in the social and organizational systems of state universities. However, as the respondents pointed out, supervisors frequently abuse their authority to further their personal agendas at the expense of other people's happiness. When asked to elaborate, respondents admitted disappointment over supervisors who go against the subordinates' desires, needs or preferences to satisfy his own needs. It is said that in this case, the power dynamics within this structure can often lead to conflicts.

Conclusions

There are varying conflict management strategies to resolving any dispute or conflict in the work place adopted by school managers. One strategy may differ from another. The difference in the strategies may be attributable to existing work climate, principles that a leader adheres to or as a response to the expectations of varying parties to conflict. Accordingly, school managers or academic leaders believe that a proactive management of conflict is necessary in order to prevent future escalation of the same into more serious ones. This is possible when leaders prepare a well-defined, strategic and organized plan on how to avoid possible onset of conflicts in the future. Respondents believe that school leaders should be visionary, looking ahead for possible solutions to problems that may occur and taking precautionary and preventive measures if possible.

Another strategy which is adherence to an established rules and standards is adopted to strengthen organizational structure and discipline in the workplace, and making sure that issues are resolved through the appropriate channels. This same mindset is shown to guarantee that decision-making practices are made in accordance with the regulations in place, to enforce fairness and equity. This response coincides with the principle that all issues are addressed fairly and equitably and according to established policies and guidelines.

When leader involves subordinates in the process of problem-solving and decision-making, he is able to create an environment of openness and inclusivity in all aspect Leaders adhere to the principle of giving opportunities to all parties to be heard and taking part in the resolution of the issues at hand. With this open communication and participative decision-making practices, no parties shall be left unsatisfied as everyone vies for a win-win solution.

Allowing the parties to resolve their differences amicably on their own allow them to do what they want to do with the hope that it will bring enlightenment to the conflict is one technique adopted by academic leaders. With this, managers expect that parties are accountable and responsible in every step of the way. This response however may not be taken lightly to mean that parties may do everything they want at all cost no matter what the consequences. This laissez -faire management style is very much a hands-off approach, which is only best for certain situations where parties are responsible enough to find solution to the problems with less or even no interference from supervisors. This is appropriate only when parties are responsible enough to take care of themselves and are mature to make a sensible decision making on their own.

Recommendations

The results of the study find its applicability to other various settings. Adoption of a more active proactive conflict management practices among school managers and leaders through regular training sessions and workshops that emphasize the significance of promptly identifying and resolving possible conflict, how to identify conflict, its root causes, and deal with problems before they escalate into more serious issues are expected of academic leaders in every organization. There must be a tailored leadership training programs focused on developing both hard skills like policy adherence and procedural knowledge and soft skills like empathy, active listening, and conflict mediation to handle diverse conflict situations effectively. Increase awareness on basic policy and issues on conflict resolution mediation and conciliation and make sure every employee is knowledgeable of the organization's conflict resolution policies and procedures by conducting information awareness campaigns and announcements and posting, programs and role-playing activities are also expected. In addition, employees should be encouraged to participate in candid dialogue and collaborative decision-making by establishing official channels where they can voice their ideas and concerns without fear of retaliation in order to foster an environment of open communication and other feedback mechanisms. Similarly, findings of this research may be applied in any research in the future as basis for similar studies using other variables not explored like extending its application to other academic leaders as well as employees and staff of other state universities, public or private or in non-academic setting. Lastly, future research may utilize results of this study to further investigate other areas such as dealing specifically with interpersonal conflicts among supervisors, subordinates and peers and exploring other conflict management styles.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were taken into account securing informed consent from respondents who were assured of their anonymity and were properly informed of the purpose of the study that the results will be confidential and will be utilized for purposes of the research only and in addition, that the respondents have the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time for whatever reasons deemed considered. In addition, there has been no conflict of interest that exists in the conduct of the study and careful consideration taken to make sure that the interpretations of the findings were made fairly and in accordance with the purpose of the research.

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REFERENCES

- Abun, D. (2021). Rule-Based Leadership-Management Style of Administrators and the Entrepreneurial Spirit of Employees. Available at SSRN 3962643.
- Anatsui, T. C., & Ojunita, L. (2015). Public Relations Proactive Approach/; Effective Institutional Conflict Management. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(7), 797-810.
- Antonakis, J., & House, R. J. (2014). Instrumental leadership: Measurement and extension of transformational–transactional leadership theory. *The leadership quarterly*, 25(4), 746-771.
- Bass, B. M., & Bass Bernard, M. (1985). Leadership and performance beyond expectations.
- Benke, M. (2023). How To Solve Conflict Situations Better with The Model of Thomas and Kilmann. *Economic and Social Development: Book of Proceedings*, 229-238.
- Blake, R. (1964). The managerial grid: The key to leadership excellence
- Castleberry, A., & Nolen, A. (2018). Thematic analysis of qualitative research data: Is it as easy as it sounds? *Currents in pharmacy teaching and learning*, 10(6), 807-815.
- Chang, Y. Y., Chang, C. Y., Chen, Y. C. K., Seih, Y. T., & Chang, S. Y. (2021). Participative leadership and unit performance: evidence for intermediate linkages. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 19(3), 355-369.
- Cornell Law School. (n.d.). laissez-faire. LII / Legal Information Institute. <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/laissez-faire>
- Doyle, Louise; McCabe, Catherine; Keogh, Brian; Brady, Annemarie; McCann, Margaret . (2019). An overview of the qualitative descriptive design within nursing research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, (), 174498711988023–.

doi:10.1177/1744987119880234

- Folger, J. P., Poole, M. S., & Stutman, R. K. (2021). *Working through conflict: Strategies for relationships, groups, and organizations*. Routledge.
- Guiab, R., & Miguel, C. (2023). Conflict Management Styles of Faculty and Staff of a State University in Northern Philippines. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(10.47191).
- Harlos, K., & Knoll, M. (2021). Employee silence and workplace bullying. Pathways of job-related negative behaviour, 201-229
- Houlihan, F. (2020). *Autocratic, Democratic and Laissez-Faire Leadership Styles: Is there a link between these Leadership Styles and Absenteeism/Withdrawal Amongst Millennials?* (Doctoral dissertation, Dublin, National College of Ireland).
- Jia, S., Qiu, Y., and Yang, C. (2021). Sustainable development goals, financial inclusion, and grain security efficiency. *Agron* 11:2542. doi: 10.3390/agronomy11122542
- Khanaki, H., & Hassanzadeh, N. (2010). Conflict management styles: The Iranian general preference compared to the Swedish. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 1(4), 419.
- London, M., Bear, J. B., Cushenbery, L., & Sherman, G. D. (2019). Leader support for gender equity: Understanding prosocial goal orientation, leadership motivation, and power sharing. *Human Resource Management Review*, 29(3), 418-427.
- Lynn Fitzpatrick, R. (2007). A literature review exploring values alignment as a proactive approach to conflict management. *International journal of conflict management*, 18(3), 280-305.
- Miao, Q., Newman, A., Schwarz, G., & Xu, L. (2013). Participative leadership and the organizational commitment of civil servants in China: The mediating effects of trust in supervisor. *British Journal of Management*, 24, S76-S92.
- Nischal, S. (2014). Application of Thomas Kilmann Conflict Resolution Mechanism for Conflict Management in HR of Manufacturing Sector. *ISS Univ.J.COM.Mgt*, 3(1), 62-70.
- Norris, K. R., Ghahremani, H., & Lemoine, G. J. (2021). Is it laissez-faire leadership or delegation? A deeper examination of an over-simplified leadership phenomenon. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 28(3), 322-339.
- Northouse, P. G. (2016). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (7th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Perkins, D. (2003). *King Arthur's round table: How collaborative conversations create smart organizations*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Sudhakar, g. P. (2023). Top-3 reasons for conflicts and top-3 conflict resolution techniques used by employees at all levels in organizations. *Climate Finance & Sustainable Development: Risk & Rewards*, 92.
- Thanh, N. H., & Quang, N. V. (2022). Transformational, transactional, laissez-faire leadership styles and employee engagement: Evidence from Vietnam's public sector. *Sage Open*, 12(2), 21582440221094606.
- Thomas, K. W., & Kilmann, R. H. (1974). *Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument*. CPP, Inc.
- Thomas, K. W. (2008). *Thomas-Kilmann conflict mode. TKI Profile and Interpretive Report*, 1(11).
- Thanh, N. H., & Quang, N. V. (2022). Transformational, transactional, laissez-faire

- leadership styles and employee engagement: Evidence from Vietnam's public sector. *Sage Open*, 12(2), 21582440221094606.
- Thomas, K. J. (1976). *Conflict and conflict management*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Wang, Q., Hou, H., & Li, Z. (2022). Participative leadership: a literature review and prospects for future research. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 924357.
- Yang, I. (2015). Positive effects of laissez-faire leadership: conceptual exploration. *Journal of Management Development*, 34(10), 1246-1261.